

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE ON POLITICAL PARTICIPATION,
POLITICAL EFFICACY AND VOTING BEHAVIOR AMONG COLLEGE
STUDENTS: EVIDENCE FROM SUKKUR DIVISION, SINDH

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of social media use on political participation, political efficacy, and voting behavior among college students in the Sukkur Division of Sindh, Pakistan. Using a quantitative survey of 386 students, the analysis included descriptive statistics, Pearson correlations, and regression models to test three hypotheses. Results indicated that social media use is strongly and positively associated with political outcomes of College Students. Social media for 58.8% of the variance in political participation and 50.4% of the variance in political efficacy and explains 26.0% of the variance in voting behavior. All three regression models were statistically significant ($p < .001$). Notably, increased social media engagement corresponded with higher self-reported confidence in understanding politics and greater offline political activity (e.g. voting, protests). These findings relate to Uses and Gratifications Theory, which suggested individuals use media to fulfill informational and civic needs and with theories of political mobilization via communication tools. The study investigated the potential of social media to empower youth politically and suggests implications for policymakers and educators. Recommended actions include integrating digital media literacy into curricula, leveraging social platforms for civic engagement, and addressing online misinformation and digital divides to foster inclusive political participation.

INTRODUCTION

Social media has fundamentally transformed political communication globally, including in developing democracies like Pakistan. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and WhatsApp have dramatically increased the spread of political information among the masses. They allowed users, especially youth, to access political news, engage in debates, organize movements, and directly interact

with political leaders (Ofei et al., 2024). In Pakistan, rising smartphone ownership and internet availability have been linked to significant increases in public political participation, notably during elections and protests (Younus et al., 2024). At the same time, scholars note that empirical evidence on how social media use affects political efficacy and participation is limited in semi-urban and rural contexts. Pakistan's

demographics emphasize the importance of youth; about 60% of the population is under 30 years old (Zeib, 2021). This youthful majority has great potential to influence elections and political discourse. Political efficacy is a belief that one can understand and influence politics. It is known to encourage participation (Ikeda, Kobayashi, & Hoshimoto, 2008). Social media enables information access and interactive discussion, social media may enhance users' internal political efficacy and motivate various forms of political engagement, such as voting, rallies, and online activism. However, most research on these dynamics has focused on urban areas, and little is known about regions like Sukkur Division, which mix urban and rural communities. This study aimed to fill this gap by examining how social media use influences political participation, efficacy, and voting behavior among college students

in Sukkur Division, Sindh. This region has seen recent improvements in digital connectivity but faces challenges such as limited educational infrastructure and economic constraints, which may affect online engagement. Without understanding how social media shapes political attitudes and behavior in such semi-urban contexts, efforts to boost youth engagement in democracy may be incomplete.

Research Objectives

- To determine the impact of social media use on political participation.
- To find out the impact of social media use on political efficacy
- To measure the impact of social media use on voting behavior.

Literature Review

Social Media and Political Participation

Social media networks offer forums where ordinary citizens can share political opinions through pages, groups, and personal accounts. Researchers argue that digital media platforms open new channels for civic engagement. For example, Karakaya and Glazier (2019) emphasize that online news sources can substitute for traditional free press and foster political activity. Similarly, Wang, Kim, and Lin (2024) finds that social media users frequently involve themselves in policy dialogues and political debates. Empirical studies have shown that internet access and online discussion can raise individuals' political awareness

and group affiliations, both important antecedents of participation (Katz et al., 1973; Verba et al., 1995). In election contexts, social media not only mobilizes existing supporters but also brings previously disengaged groups into conversation (Schwitter, 2024). For instance, youth active on social networks during the 2008 and 2012 U.S. elections were more likely to vote and campaign (Boulianne & Larsson, 2024). In Asia and the Middle East, social media played a key role in movements like the Arab Spring, linking protesters and spreading information (Moss & Bath, 2024; Saud & Ashfaq, 2024). However, challenges such as the digital divide and misinformation can suppress engagement, particularly

among disadvantaged communities (Hoffmann & Lutz, 2021; García del Horno et al., 2024).

Social Media and Political Efficacy

Political efficacy refers to citizens' belief in their capacity to understand and influence political processes. Studies indicate a significant relationship between social media use and political efficacy (Alarqan, 2020). Online platforms allow users to follow political news, interact with officials, and observe civic campaigns, which can reinforce confidence in their political competence (Katz et al., 1973). Empirical evidence shows mixed but generally positive effects: some research finds frequent visits to news and social media sites raise internal political efficacy (Zhang et al., 2024), though others caution that certain online experiences (e.g., browsing government sites) may temporarily reduce feelings of external efficacy. Overall, higher levels of efficacy are associated with greater political involvement (Kenski & Stroud, 2006; Stauffer, 2021). Thus, there is reason to believe that social media engagement can boost students' sense of empowerment in politics.

Social Media and Voting Behavior

Voting behavior, as an outcome of political engagement, is influenced by many factors, including media consumption. The literature on social media and voting suggests that exposure to political content online can shape voters' decisions. Supriyanto, T. (2024) notes that modern social media serve as platforms for political information and debate, potentially affecting both online and offline participation. Studies show that social media activity can increase turnout: for example, social media users in Indonesia and Pakistan were more politically active and likely to vote (Monzel et al., 2025). In Pakistan's context, the 2013 and 2018 elections saw a surge in digital campaigning and voter outreach. Nevertheless, some research argues that translating online activism into actual votes can be complex, given other influences on individual voting choices such as ideology, issues, and social networks. Understanding these dynamics in a semi-urban Pakistani setting is a goal of the present study.

Youth Political Engagement in Pakistan

In Pakistan, young people form a demographic majority and have shown growing political interest, especially through digital media. Surveys indicate many Pakistani youths follow political content online and use social networks to express opinions (Jawed et al., 2023). Studies in major cities (Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore) have found that social media contributes to youth political awareness and efficacy. However, research on rural or semi-urban areas like Sukkur is scarce. Factors such as limited technology access and lower digital literacy may constrain engagement in these regions. In Sindh province, where politics often involves dynasty and tribal elements, social media may offer alternative spaces for youth to connect and participate. This study helps illuminate these understudied dynamics by focusing on college students outside the major metropolitan centers.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on **Uses and Gratifications Theory** (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973) and insights from the **Civic Voluntarism Model** (Verba, Schlozman, & Brady, 1995). Uses and Gratifications Theory holds that media users actively seek content to satisfy needs such as information, identity, social interaction, or entertainment. In a political context, this suggests that students use social media to meet informational needs, engage in political discussions, and express civic interests. Unlike earlier models of passive audiences, UGT emphasizes that individuals selectively use media to enhance their political engagement. For example, a student may follow a political news page to learn about policies or join an online debate group to fulfill a need for social connection and civic expression.

The Civic Voluntarism Model identifies three key factors driving political participation: **resources** (time, money, skills), **political engagement** (interest and efficacy), and **recruitment networks** (invitations to participate). Social media can influence all three: it provides low-cost access to political information (enhancing skills), exposes users to political discussions that can boost efficacy (the belief in one's political influence), and expands networks through peer sharing and group memberships (serving as informal recruitment pathways). Together, these

theories suggest that active social media use should increase students' political efficacy and participation by fulfilling needs and lowering barriers to engagement.

Although much is known about social media and political behavior in urbanized settings, significant **research gaps** remain. Few studies have focused on semi-urban or rural regions like Sukkur Division, and empirical evidence is sparse on how social media specifically affects political efficacy (beyond mere participation) among Pakistani college students. Existing literature often treats social media use as a single construct, but types of use (passive browsing vs. active posting) may have different impacts. By integrating UGT and the Civic Voluntarism Model, this study provides a theoretically informed, contextually grounded analysis of how college students in Sukkur Division use social media for political purposes and how this relates to their beliefs and actions. This approach offers new insights for policy, education, and civic strategies in similar regional contexts.

Methodology

This study used a quantitative survey design to examine the relationship between social media use and political outcomes among college students in Sukkur Division (Sukkur, Khairpur, and Ghotki). convenience sampling technique ensured representation from urban and semi-urban degree

colleges, with final-year students randomly selected. A total of 386 valid responses were obtained. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering demographics, social media usage, political efficacy, participation, and voting behavior, using five-point Likert scales. Surveys were administered in classrooms with informed consent, ensuring anonymity and voluntary participation. Data were analyzed using SPSS, starting with descriptive statistics, followed by Pearson's correlations and multiple linear regressions to test the influence of social media on political engagement metrics while controlling demographics. Ethical protocols, including confidentiality and institutional permissions, were strictly followed to protect participants and ensure the validity of results.

Results

this study examined college students in Sukkur Division, the descriptive statistics. In this study (Table 1) revealed that the majority of respondents are young (54.7% aged 18–20) and predominantly male (72.8%), with education levels mainly clustered at B.Sc. (38.3%) and M.A. (40.7%). Facebook is the most preferred social media platform (66.6%), and while 38.6% of students primarily use social media for education, only 13% use it explicitly for politics. These patterns align with global trends, where younger populations often use social media chiefly for social connection, entertainment, and education, while political use remains secondary (Boulianne, 2020; Barati, 2023).

Table 01 Descriptive Statistics

Question	Option	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	18-20	211	54.7	54.7	54.7
	21-23	146	37.8	37.8	92.5
	24-26	15	3.9	3.9	96.4
	26 to above	14	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	386	100.0	100.0	100.0
Gender	Male	281	72.8	72.8	72.8
	Female	105	27.2	27.2	100.0
	Total	386	100.0	100.0	
Qualification	B. A	40	10.4	10.40	10.4
	B.Sc.	148	38.3	38.3	48.7
	B. Com	41	10.6	10.6	59.3
	M.A	157	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	386	100.0	100.0	

Political Affiliation	PPP	80	20.7	20.7	20.7
	PML(N)	10	2.6	2.6	23.3
	PTI	126	32.6	32.6	56.0
	GDA	12	3.1	3.1	59.1
	Other	158	40.9	40.9	100.0
	Total	386	100.0		
Purpose of Social Media Usage	Talk	64	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Education	149	38.6	38.6	55.2
	Politics	50	13.0	13.0	68.1
	Entertainment	123	31.9	31.9	100.0
	Total	386	100.0	100.0	
Preferred social media platforms among students	Facebook	257	66.6	66.6	66.6
	Twitter	29	7.5	7.5	74.1
	YouTube	25	6.5	6.5	80.6
	Instagram	52	13.5	13.5	94.0
	WhatsApp	23	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	386	100.0	100.0	

(Table 2) established a high internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = .918$), exceeding the standard threshold of .70 suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), indicating the scales used to measure political participation, efficacy, and voting behavior are robust and dependable.

Table 02 Reliability Statistics

Measure	Cronbach’s α	N of Items
Combined Scale	.918	31

The regression analysis (Tables 3) show that social media use significantly predicts political participation ($R^2 = .588$), political efficacy ($R^2 = .504$), and voting behavior ($R^2 = .260$). The strongest effect is on political participation ($\beta = .767$), followed by efficacy ($\beta = .710$), with voting behavior having a more modest but still significant relationship ($\beta = .510$).

Table 03 Regression Analysis.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error		
I	.767	.588	.582	.647		
II	.710	.504	.497	.709		
III	.510	.260	.250	.866		
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares (Reg)	df	Mean Square (Reg)	F	Sig.	
I	41.720	1	41.720	99.741	.000b	
	29.280 (Res)	70	.418			
II	35.807	1	35.807	71.220	.000b	
	35.193 (Res)	70	.503			
III	18.470	1	18.470	24.612	.000b	
	52.530 (Res)	70	.750			
Coefficient						
Model	Dependent Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
I	Political Participation	.767	.077	.767	9.987	.000 ^b

II	Political Efficacy	.710	.084	.710	8.439	.000 ^b
III	Voting Behavior	.510	.103	.510	4.961	.000 ^b

Furthermore, these Table No 04 revealed strong relationships between social media use and both political participation (.767) and political efficacy (.710), but a relatively weaker direct correlation with voting behavior (.510). Interestingly, political efficacy also correlates strongly with voting behavior (.574).

Table 4. Pearson Correlation

	Social Media Use	Political Participation	Political Efficacy	Voting Behavior
Social media Use	1			
Political Participation	.767**	1		
Political Efficacy	.710**	.576**	1	
Political Voting	.510**	.174	.574**	1

Discussion

The analyses strongly support the study’s hypotheses. Active social media use among college students in Sukkur Division is associated with higher political efficacy and participation, and to a lesser extent, with increased voting behavior. The regression results confirm that social media engagement is a significant predictor of each outcome. In particular, about 59% of the variation in political participation and 50% of the variation in political efficacy are explained by differences in social media use. These are large effect sizes for social science data, indicating that online engagement is a major factor in students’ civic involvement.

These findings align with the **Uses and Gratifications Theory**, which holds that individuals deliberately use media to fulfill needs like information and social connection. Students reported using social media for educational and political information, and the strong positive associations suggest that these platforms indeed enhance their political knowledge and confidence. For example, Katz et al. (1973) argued that self-selected media use reinforces the user’s goals; here, students using social media to learn about politics likely feel more empowered to participate. Similarly, the results echo Mobilization Theory (as in Verba et al., 1995) by showing that communication tools lower barriers: social media provide resources (information and networks) that translate into real-world activities.

The correlation matrix reveals interesting nuances. While social media use is strongly correlated with both participation and efficacy, the direct correlation

between participation and voting was weak and non-significant. This suggests that, among this sample, being active online or engaged in politics does not automatically guarantee voting. Voting behavior may depend on additional factors such as personal motivation, campaign effects, or socio-economic constraints. It may also reflect that some students feel efficacious or participate in discussions but still do not turn out to vote.

Demographically, the sample was predominantly young (18–23) and slightly male-skewed. While gender differences were not the focus, the balanced representation from Sukkur, Khairpur, and Ghotki means the findings are not driven by a single urban center. The high usage of Facebook indicates that it is likely the main conduct for political content among students; this has practical implications for where political messages reach youth.

Overall, the study highlights the empowering role of social media for young citizens in a semi-urban Pakistani context. It demonstrates that online political engagement is positively linked to students’ sense of efficacy and their participation. At the same time, the results underscore the importance of addressing issues like misinformation and the digital divide. Even as social media can mobilize youth, unequal access to the internet or exposure to false information could limit who benefits from this empowerment. These considerations are addressed in the recommendations below.

Conclusion

This research examined how social media use affects political efficacy, participation, and voting behavior among college students in Sindh's Sukkur Division. The findings clearly indicate that social media plays a significant, positive role in shaping students' political perceptions and actions. In line with the stated hypotheses, greater social media engagement was associated with higher internal political efficacy and more active political participation. Students who frequently use platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter reported feeling more confident in their political knowledge and believing they can influence outcomes. They were also more likely to engage in political discussions and activities, both online and offline.

These results support theoretical expectations. According to Uses and Gratifications Theory, people use media to satisfy needs such as gaining knowledge and expressing identity; here, students' social media use fulfilled civic and informational needs, translating into confidence and action. The Civic Voluntarism Model also offers insight: by providing information and networks, social media effectively enhances the resources, skills, and recruitment that drive participation. In short, active digital engagement appears to empower youth in their political involvement.

However, the study also highlights challenges. Notably, the indirect link between participation and voting suggests that online activity alone may not ensure electoral participation. Additionally, the presence of a "digital divide" means that not all young people have equal access to these empowering tools. Issues of misinformation and low-quality political discourse online may also dampen the positive effects. The findings have important implications for Pakistan's democratic development. They suggest that efforts to strengthen democracy should leverage social media's reach among youth while also educating students to be critical consumers of online content.

Recommendations

Colleges and educators should integrate digital media literacy and civic education into their programs. Workshops or courses can teach students how to critically analyze political content, recognize

misinformation, and engage responsibly online. This will help students use social media constructively and avoid echo chambers.

Political parties, government bodies, and civil society organizations should actively use social platforms to involve young people in democratic processes. For example, they can run voter registration drives, online debates, and awareness campaigns through the social media channels most used by students (notably Facebook). Engaging youth through the media they trust can increase their turnout and activism.

Policymakers and infrastructure planners should work to reduce the digital divide. This includes expanding affordable, high-speed internet access in rural and semi-urban areas of Sindh. When more students (regardless of background) have reliable access, a broader segment of youth can participate politically through digital means.

Stakeholders should launch awareness campaigns on verifying sources and avoiding fake news. Social media companies, in partnership with educational institutions, can provide guidance on fact-checking and encourage sharing of credible political content. Promoting a more informed online dialogue will help ensure that social media engagement translates into healthy civic involvement.

Future studies should explore these issues using diverse methods. Longitudinal research could examine how online engagement translates into long-term political participation. Qualitative studies or experiments could investigate causal mechanisms, such as how specific social media features influence efficacy. Special attention should be given to marginalized youth to understand how to engage them effectively.

References

- Alarqan, A. (2020). Impact of social media and political participation on political efficacy of political science students of Al al-Bayt University. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 14(8), 295-307.
- Barati, A. (2023). *Exercising Authority and Representing Rule, Eighteenth-Century Persian decrees from the Shrine of Imam Reza in Mashhad* (Vol. 25)

- Boulianne, S. (2020). Twenty years of digital media effects on civic and political participation. *Communication research*, 47(7), 947-966.
- Boulianne, S., & Larsson, A. O. (2024). Comparative digital political communication: Comparisons across countries, platforms, and time. *Social Science Computer Review*, 42(5), 1092-1100.
- García del Horno, R., Rico, G., & Hernández, E. (2024). Do they feel like they don't matter? The rural-urban divide in external political efficacy. *West European Politics*, 47(7), 1447-1472.
- Hoffmann, C. P., & Lutz, C. (2021). Digital divides in political participation: The mediating role of social media self-efficacy and privacy concerns. *Policy & Internet*, 13(1), 6-29.
- Ikeda, K. I., Kobayashi, T., & Hoshimoto, M. (2008). Does political participation make a difference? The relationship between political choice, civic engagement and political efficacy. *Electoral Studies*, 27(1), 77-88.
- Jawed, R., Lodhi, M. S., & Salim, M. (2023). Youth Engagement and Political Activism in Contemporary Pakistan: A Sociopolitical Analysis. *Pakistan JL Analysis & Wisdom*, 2, 224.
- Karakaya, S., & Glazier, R. A. (2019). Media, information, and political participation: The importance of online news sources in the absence of a free press. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 16(3), 290-306.
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *The public opinion quarterly*, 37(4), 509-523.
- Kenski, K., & Stroud, N. J. (2006). Connections between Internet use and political efficacy, knowledge, and participation. *Journal of broadcasting & electronic media*, 50(2), 173-192.
- Monzel, M., Grünhage, T., & Reuter, M. (2025). Is issue voting solely based on issues? Latent factors of political ideology in response patterns of voting advice applications. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 1-11.
- Moss, D. M., & Bath, C. (2024). Civic opportunities and democratic practices in Yemen and Libya after the Arab Spring. *Qualitative Sociology*, 47(2), 187-220.
- Ofei, O., Kayode, E., Apeakhuye, A. L., Precious, O. E., & Emuke, E. (2024). A Review of Social Media as Alternative Medium for Political Participation. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 5(1), 489-497.
- Saud, M., & Ashfaq, A. (2024). Shift from traditional to contemporary political patterns: Knowing the youth perspectives on political participation. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 00219096241235292.
- Schwitter, N. (2024). How offline meetings affect online activities: the case of Wikipedia. *EPJ Data Science*, 13(1), 67.
- Stauffer, K. E. (2021). Public perceptions of women's inclusion and feelings of political efficacy. *American Political Science Review*, 115(4), 1226-1241.
- Supriyanto, T. (2024). The Influence of Social Media on Political Participation in the Digital Era. *International Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 1(1), 43-54.
- Verba, S., Schlozman, K. L., & Brady, H. E. (1995). *Voice and equality: Civic voluntarism in American politics*. Harvard University Press.
- Wang, Y., Kim, Y., & Lin, H. (2024). Social viewing of news and political participation: The mediating roles of information acquisition, self-expression, and partisan identity. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 154, 108158.
- Younus, M., Nurmandi, A., Mutiarin, D., Luhur Prianto, A., Abdul Manaf, H., & Irawan, B. (2024). Running Digital Political Marketing Movement for Election 2024: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Political Marketing*, 1-23.
- Zeib, F. (2021). Rising wave of social media: A perspective of political awareness, voting behavior, online and offline political participation of university students in Pakistan.

Zhang, B., Holton, A. E., & Gil de Zúñiga, H. (2024). Finding “fake” in the news: the relationship between social media use, political knowledge, epistemic political efficacy and fake news literacy. *Online Information Review*, 48(7), 1470-1487.

